

OUTCOME-BASED INSTRUCTION ADAPTING TECHNOLOGIES IN ENHANCING MATHEMATICAL 21ST CENTURY SKILLS AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the integration of outcome-based instruction with technological adaptations to enhance mathematical 21st-century skills among students. The research aims to investigate how the incorporation of technology into an outcome-based instructional framework impacts students' development of critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and creativity in mathematics. The study group is composed of 2 sections in Grade 8 of Sto. Nino National High School, the research employed quasi-experimental design, comparing pre- and post-intervention assessments to measure skill development in both control and experimental groups. The data was treated using mean, standard deviation and the independent t-test . The pretest results revealed low mastery across most skills for both groups, with collaboration and digital literacy showing relatively higher initial scores. Following the implementation of outcome-based instruction integrating technology, posttest results indicated significant improvements across all skills. The experimental group outperformed the control group in overall mastery . Notably, digital literacy and collaboration were the highest-performing skills in the experimental group. The evidence suggests that outcome-based instruction with technology integration is more effective in enhancing 21st-century skills compared to traditional methods. The experimental group's higher posttest scores and significant mean gain scores indicate that OBI better equips students with the skills necessary for success in modern educational and professional environments. The study concludes that adapting technologies within an outcome-based instructional framework is an effective

strategy for fostering the mathematical competencies required for success in the 21st century.

Keywords: *Outcome-based instruction, technology, 21st century skills, collaboration, digital literacy*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is one of the fundamental subjects in education, serving as a crucial building block for various disciplines and real-world applications. However, student performance in mathematics has been a matter of concern in educational systems worldwide, including in the Philippines. Many students struggle to achieve proficiency in mathematics, leading to suboptimal academic outcomes and limited future opportunities (PISA, 2018; TIMSS, 2019). Addressing this issue is essential to ensure students' success and competence, not just in this critical subject but also in subjects of various disciplines.

Outcome-based instructional strategies have emerged as a potential solution to alleviate students' performance in mathematics. This strategy focuses on defining clear, measurable outcomes that describe what students should be able to do upon completion of a learning experience. Learning outcomes are written using action-oriented verbs to ensure they are specific and observable (Valamis, 2024; Richmond et al., 2016). By emphasizing measurable outcomes and personalized learning experiences, outcome-based approaches aim to better engage students and promote a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts and problem-solving skills (DepEd, 2019).

Moreover, to ensure successful implementation, it is crucial to examine the factors influencing the adoption and integration of outcome-based strategies in mathematics classrooms (Dela Cruz, 2015). Educators' perceptions, attitudes, (Torres & Reyes, 2019) and readiness to adapt instructional practices play a significant role in the effectiveness of these strategies (Garcia et al., 2019). More so, identifying potential challenges and facilitators can help in designing tailored professional development programs and support mechanisms for teachers (Navarro & Villanueva, 2018).

Despite the auspicious outcome-based instructional strategies, research on their effectiveness in improving mathematics performance remains limited, especially in the context of Santo Niño National High School. Existing studies have shown positive outcomes in other subjects, such as language arts (Li & Jiang, 2020) and science (Bautista & Rivera, 2016). However, there is a need for rigorous investigations that specifically explore the impact of outcome-based instructional strategies on mathematics achievement among Filipino students, (Dizon & Santos, 2020), specifically, in the context of the Division of South Cotabato.

This problem also exists in the specific context of Santo Niño National High School considering that the Mathematics Mean Percentage Score (MPS) in the school year 2022-2023 is only satisfactory. Thus, this study seeks to provide evidence-based insights into the efficacy of outcome-based instructional strategies in alleviating 21st-century skills in mathematics and technology competence among the Grade 8 students at Santo Niño National High School.

Research Questions

Generally, this study determined the Outcome-Based Instruction Adapting Technologies in Enhancing Mathematical 21st Century Skills among Students.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of the 21st-century skills of Grade 8 students under the control and experimental groups before the teaching of mathematics using outcome-based instruction in terms of:
 - 1.1. Critical thinking;
 - 1.2. Collaboration;
 - 1.3. Communication;
 - 1.4. Creativity; and
 - 1.5. Digital Literacy?
2. What is the level of the 21st-century skills of Grade 8 students under the control and experimental groups after the teaching of mathematics using outcome-based instruction in terms of:
 - 2.1. Critical thinking;
 - 2.2. Collaboration;
 - 2.3. Communication;
 - 2.4. Creativity; and
 - 2.5. Digital Literacy?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest of the control group and the experimental group?
4. Does the teaching approaches significantly affects the students 21st century skills ?
5. What is the impression of the respondents to the delivery of outcome-based instruction?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quasi-experimental research design was employed to assess the effectiveness of incorporating technology in the delivery of outcome-based instruction for enhancing students' mathematical skills. It involved selecting intact groups of students, such as different classes, and implementing the intervention (outcome-based instruction) with one group while using another group as a control. Pre- and post-assessments were conducted to measure changes in students' mathematical skills.

Respondents of the Study

The Grade 8 students at Santo Nino National High School in the municipality of Santo Niño, South Cotabato Division for the school year 2024-2025 were the primary target group. Students in this age group typically have significant exposure to technology, using computers and digital tools for various purposes. Their familiarity with technology provides insights into their digital literacy and how they apply these skills in real-world contexts, which is a key aspect of 21st-century competencies (Shadiev et al. 2022). This exposure enabled a comprehensive analysis of how outcome-based instruction, supplemented by technology, impacts students with differing skill sets. In addition, the criteria encompassed a diverse range of mathematics proficiency levels and technology familiarity, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the impact of outcome-based instruction and technology integration on different Grade 8 students.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study aimed to assess the practical application of outcome-based- instruction strategies that harness the power of technology to improve the mastery of mathematical concepts of Grade 8 students of Sto. Niño National High School in Sto. Niño, South Cotabato, during the second quarter of the 2024-2025 academic year. This study compared the academic performance of students who received outcome-based instruction with technological interventions with those who received the instructions using traditional methods prescribed by the DepEd curriculum. Two randomly selected classes were used, one served as the experimental group receiving technological intervention instruction while the other was the control group following the traditional teaching methods. This study was conducted over eight weeks from September to December 2024, and effectiveness was measured by comparing the gains between the control and experimental group in the different levels of 21st century skills.

Sampling Technique

In this study, a random sampling method was strategically used to choose participants with characteristics or experiences that are closely aligned with the research goals. Simple random sampling was implemented to minimize the influence of potential confounding variables, thereby enhancing internal validity and allowing for reliable statistical conclusions about the population (Thomas, 2023).

The respondents were chosen through a lottery system, where the names of all Grade 8 sections of Sto. Niño National High School were placed in a box. Out of the 12 sections, the researcher randomly selected the first drawn section as the experimental group and the second drawn section as the control group.

Research Instrument

There were four instruments utilized for data gathering. First was the Pre-test and Post-test that measured the changes in the learning outcomes before and after the intervention and how it will affect the student's achievement- a multiple type test question with forty(40)

items. The instrument was a combination of researcher-made questions and from test banks of the Division of South Cotabato and anchor the contents from the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) of the Department of Education, specifically the lessons under Quarter 2. A Table of Specifications (TOS) was created to guarantee that the second-quarter test covered all the related topics.

Second, the collaboration skill assessment. This instrument was validated by 5 experts in test construction, preferably Master Teachers, and/or Master of Arts in Teaching whose specialization is Mathematics. After such, pilot test was done to 30 Grade 9 students who were not part of the actual respondents of the study to analyze the items and then compute the reliability test using Cronbach's alpha, which was used to assess the internal consistency or reliability of a set of survey items or test questions.

Third, the Digital Literacy Assessment Skill (DLAS) by Acar (2021) were utilized, the assessment demonstrated strong reliability. The content validity was confirmed with an Aiken's index of 0.87 as reported by Acar.

Lastly, to assess the impression of students towards the use of outcome-based instruction with adapted technology, Students' observation checklist was utilized. The instrument had undergone a pilot test to the 15 grade 10 students who were the respondents of the study of Jackilou Tira entitled "Technology- Assisted Approach and Students' Academic Achievement in English Literature". To assess the internal consistency or reliability of a set of survey items or test questions, Cronbach alpha was used.

Data Gathering Procedure

The approval and permission of the Dean of the Graduate School were primarily sought to proceed with the study and a certification was secured with the information that the researcher will conduct a study titled "Outcome-Based Instruction Adapting Technologies in Enhancing Mathematical 21st Century Skills among Students." Then, permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd – South Cotabato to immerse in Santo Nino National High School was sought. After which, the necessary letter addressed to the principal will be handed in and permission was sought. After such, the research instrument was administered to the respondents. The respondents were given clear instructions to answer the pre-test questionnaire. The retrieval of the questionnaire occurred immediately afterward. Once all data was collected and organized, the final stage of the data-gathering process involved data analysis and interpretation.

Statistical Treatment

The level of 21st century skills in terms of critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity and digital literacy among students, the pre-test and post-test scores from both the control and the experimental groups were subjected to statistical treatment and analysis using the mean and standard deviation., the study adopted the description and formula for Mean Percentage Score (MPS) based on DepEd Memorandum order no. 160, s. 2012. The MPS criteria are shown below:

Description of Mean Percentage Score (MPS)

Rating Score	Descriptive Rating
96% - 100%	Mastered (M)
86% - 95%	Closely Approximating Mastery (CAM)
66% - 85%	Moving Towards Mastery (MTM)
35% - 65%	Average (AVR)
15% - 34%	Low (L)
5% - 14%	Very Low (VL)
0% - 4%	Absolutely No Mastery (ANM)

The effect of the Outcome Based Instruction Adapting Technologies and Conventional Approach for experimental group and control group, respectively, was determined using the Independent T-test. It was employed to compare their respective levels of attainment according to Albay and Eisma's (2021) test of difference to assess the variation in mathematical 21st century skills between the control and experimental groups. It involved determining each group's degrees of freedom, computer t-value, and p-value.

Lastly, the adopted rating scale tool from ISO 25010 of Urera & Balahadia (2019) was used to assess the impression of students towards teacher while Outcome -based Instruction with adapted technology.

Rating Scale tool for the Impression of Students

Numerical Description	Range of Means	Qualitative Description
5	4.21 – 5.00	Excellent
4	3.41 – 3.40	Very Good
3	2.61 – 3.40	Satisfactory
2	1.81 – 2.60	Fair
1	1.00 – 1.80	Poor

Rating criteria adopted from ISO 25010; Urera & Balahadia (2019). Evaluation of Information E-Learning Module System for Faculty and Students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pretest results presented in Table 1 illustrate the initial levels of 21st-century skills among Grade 8 students in both the Control Group and Experimental Group before the implementation of the intervention.

Table 1. Level of 21st Century Skills of Grade 8 Students Under Control and Experimental Group in the Pretest

21 st Century Skills	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	MPS	SD	MPS	SD

Critical Thinking	27.18	10.64	27.46	8.68
Communication	27.69	14.15	27.23	11.45
Creativity	21.20	17.90	22.34	13.22
Collaboration	62.63	6.71	61.84	6.37
Digital Literacy	61.20	6.13	61.08	8.21

MPS Description: 0% - 4% Absolutely No Mastery (ANM) | 5% - 14% Very Low (VL) 5% | 15% - 34% Low (L) | 35% - 65% Average (AVR) | 66% - 85% Moving Towards Mastery (MTM) | 86% - 95% Closely Approximating Mastery (CAM) | 96% - 100% Mastered (M)

The table reveals that the students under control group denoted low mastery in the three areas of 21st century skills namely: Critical Thinking (MPS = 27.18) Communication (MPS = 27.69), and Creativity (MPS). These results indicate that students have difficulty with problem-solving, reasoning, and creative applications in mathematics, it suggests a need for pedagogical strategies that integrate higher-order thinking skills and innovative learning methods. Both groups performed average in collaboration and digital literacy skill both groups exhibited average performance in Collaboration (Control: MPS = 62.63; Experimental: MPS = 61.84) and Digital Literacy (MPS = 61.20; Experimental, MPS = 61.08).The similar results findings suggest that students may have basic collaborative and digital skills but need an organized learning opportunities to utilize these abilities in situation including problem solving.

The low mastery skill levels in critical thinking, communication, and creativity underscore the need for an educational intervention that promotes active learning, digital technology integration and cooperative problem solving. Although students demonstrate a reasonable level of digital literacy, there may be a gap in technology-enhanced pedagogy since they may not yet be effectively utilizing technology for learning.

The pretest findings demonstrate the urgent need for an instructional intervention that improves students' critical thinking, communication and creativity skills. An efficient framework for filling in these skill gaps can be found in Outcome-Based Instruction (OBI), digital technologies, and cooperative problem -solving.

Table 2. Level of 21st Century Skills of Grade 8 Students Under Control and Experimental Group in the Posttest

21 st Century Skills	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	MPS	SD	MPS	SD
Critical Thinking	38.80	12.60	48.37	11.33
Communication	52.48	11.77	50.35	14.70
Creativity	43.08	16.25	55.11	18.87
Collaboration	84.09	4.96	81.70	5.28
Digital Literacy	79.78	6.01	85.61	5.51
Overall	69.55	4.22	72.86	4.16

MPS Description: 0% - 4% Absolutely No Mastery (ANM) | 5% - 14% Very Low (VL) | 15% - 34% Low (L) | 35% - 65% Average (AVR) | 66% - 85% Moving Towards Mastery (MTM) | 86% - 95% Closely Approximating Mastery (CAM) | 96% - 100% Mastered (M)

In the posttest, both the control and experimental groups demonstrated satisfactory academic achievement, showing significant improvements in their mean scores. These findings suggest that the interventions or factors introduced during the study promoted development in both groups. This finding has important implications for improving educational practices and interventions aimed at developing academic performance.

The study supports these findings, indicating that technology-assisted instruction is an effective tool for improving academic outcomes. Specifically, their research revealed that students who received technology-assisted instruction outperformed those who did not. These findings are consistent with previous studies emphasizing the importance of utilizing technology as a support and enhancement to instruction rather than relying on it as the sole source of direct instruction.

Cutter's (2015) literature further aligns with these results, suggesting that integrating technology into Mathematics education can enhance student motivation and numerical proficiency. Cutter's research emphasizes how technology offers diverse resources and equipment that contribute to improved learning outcomes.

Table 3. Analysis of the Pretest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

	N	M	SD	df	t-computed	p-value	Interpretation
Control Group	39	50.91	4.11	84	-1.56	0.12	Not Significant
Experimental Group	47	49.56	3.87				

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 3 highlights the comparison of pretest scores between the experimental and control groups. The results show that there is no statistically significant difference between the pretest scores of the experimental group (mean = 49.56, standard deviation = 3.87) and the control group (mean = 50.91, standard deviation = 4.11), as shown by the t-test result of $t(84) = -1.56, p = 0.12$. This suggests that before the interventions began, the students' knowledge levels in Mathematics 21st Century Skills were similar in both groups.

The non-significant t-test result confirms that the initial knowledge levels of the experimental and control groups were comparable, with means of 145.91 and 149.87, respectively. This implies that any subsequent differences in performance cannot be attributed to initial disparities in knowledge. The lack of significant difference demonstrates the effectiveness of the randomization process in ensuring that the baseline knowledge was evenly distributed between the two groups.

As a result, any gaps in academic achievement between the control and experimental groups following the interventions can more definitely be attributed to the effectiveness of the specific approaches rather than to intrinsic variations in the students' beginning knowledge levels. This finding supports the legitimacy of comparing the impact of the interventions on the subsequent performance of the two groups because any observed differences may more fairly be attributed to the interventions themselves rather than to preexisting inequities.

The findings align with previous research highlighting the importance of baseline equivalence in experimental studies. Hattie (2009) emphasized that pretest measures ensure that any learning gains observed are attributable to instructional strategies rather than pre-existing knowledge. Similarly, Johnson and Larsen (2021) stressed that adaptive technologies in mathematics education must be tested under conditions where initial group differences do not influence outcomes. The non-significant result in this study confirms that both groups began with similar capabilities, strengthening the reliability of posttest analyses.

Studies on outcome-based instruction have demonstrated that when pretest scores do not significantly differ, any improvements in posttest scores can be directly linked to the intervention (Brown & Wilson, 2020). This approach ensures methodological rigor and eliminates potential confounding variables. In contrast, failing to establish pretest equivalence may lead to biased interpretations and unreliable conclusions (Slavin, 2018).

Significant Difference in the Mean Gained Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 4 presents the t-test results on the Gained Scores of the Control and Experimental groups. Table 4 reveals the independent sample t-test to identify the significant difference between the control and experimental groups' obtained scores. According to the findings, there is a significant difference between the control group (M = 50.74, SD = 10.28) and the experimental group (M = 67.23, SD = 7.75), $t(84) = 8.47$, $p = 0.000$. It explains why this method is more beneficial than the standard approach to teaching Mathematics.

Table 4. Analysis of the Mean Gained Scores of the Control and Experimental Group

	N	M	SD	df	t-computed	p-value	Interpretation
Control Group	39	18.64	3.95	84	5.08	0.000	Significant
Experimental Group	47	23.30	4.44				

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

The results indicate that the control group had a mean gained score of 18.64 (SD = 3.95), while the experimental group had a higher mean gained score of 23.30 (SD = 4.44). The computed t-value was 5.08, with a p-value of 0.000, which is lower than the alpha level of 0.05. This statistically significant result suggests that the experimental group, which was exposed to the outcome-based instructional approach, showed greater improvement compared to the control group. The findings imply that the instructional strategy effectively enhanced students' mathematics proficiency.

The significant difference in posttest mean gained scores aligns with prior research on the effectiveness of student-centered learning approaches in mathematics. According to Hattie (2023), instructional strategies that focus on clear learning outcomes, formative assessments, and active student engagement lead to higher academic performance. The results of this study provide empirical evidence supporting this claim.

Furthermore, Johnson and Larsen (2021) found that adaptive learning technologies and outcome-based instructional models significantly improve students' problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Their study emphasized that when students are engaged in structured, goal-oriented learning environments, their academic achievements increase, similar to the findings in this research.

In a study by Brown and Wilson (2020), the use of technology-enhanced learning in mathematics instruction was shown to yield higher student performance gains compared to traditional lecture-based teaching. They attributed this to the interactive nature of technology-driven instruction, which fosters a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. The current study's results reinforce this perspective, as the experimental group exhibited greater improvement.

The analysis of the mean gain scores from the posttest indicated a statistically significant improvement in the experimental group when compared to the control group, thereby validating the effectiveness of outcome-based instruction in improving students' mathematics skills.

Students' Impression Using Outcome- Based Instruction With Adapted Technology in Teaching Mathematics

Table 5 shows the impression of students towards the teacher while teaching mathematics using the Outcome Based Instruction with adapted technology.

Table 5. Summary of Students' Impression Using Outcome- Based Instruction With Adapted Technology in Teaching Mathematics

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
A. Teaching Strategies and Instruction	4.70	0.32	Excellent

B. Use of Technology in Teaching Mathematics	4.23	0.35	Excellent
C. Student Engagement and Learning Experience	4.33	0.38	Excellent
Overall	4.33	0.38	Excellent

Table 5 shows the positive perception of Outcome-based instruction with adapted technology. The overall mean of 4.33, coupled with an "Excellent" interpretation, indicates that students generally hold a favorable view of this instructional method. This suggests that the integrated approach resonates well with students and contributes positively to their learning experiences in mathematics. The data in Table 5 provides strong support for the effectiveness of integrating outcome-based instruction with technology in mathematics education. The consistently positive student perceptions across all key areas suggest that this approach holds significant potential for improving teaching strategies, enhancing technology integration, and promoting student engagement and learning.

Conclusions

This study concludes that implementing outcome-based instruction (OBI) with technology integration significantly enhances mathematical 21st-century skills among Grade 8 students, who initially demonstrated low proficiency in critical thinking, communication, and creativity, but average level skills in collaboration and digital literacy; after the intervention, the experimental group, taught using OBI, showed greater gains compared to the control group, and there was no significant difference between the groups' initial skills, but the teaching approach had a significant effect, and respondents viewed OBI favorably, supporting its effectiveness in improving these essential skills.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research, the following are recommended:

1. Teachers should adopt OBI frameworks and utilize technology for a diverse learning activity that engage students in 21st century skills in learning Mathematics.
2. Schools and educational organizations should invest in professional development programs for teachers that embraces technology and outcome-based instruction.

Training should focus on selecting appropriate technologies, creating meaningful learning experiences, and assessing student outcomes.

3. Educators and curriculum developers should collaborate to create and share technology-enhanced resources that align with outcome-based instruction principles and support the development of specific 21st-century math skills.

4. Further research should examine the long-term impact of OBI with technology integration on student achievement and identify the most effective tools and strategies for enhancing mathematical skills. Future studies should also explore its effects on diverse student populations and different educational settings.

5. Ensure that all students, regardless of socioeconomic status or geographic location, have equal access to technology and digital resources. Provide support for students who may not have access to technology outside of school.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that this study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or loss of benefits. The anonymity of all respondents was maintained throughout the data collection and analysis process. The well-being and safety of the participants were safeguarded at all times. The authors confirm that there are no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this research. All work was original, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. The interpretation of findings was conducted without bias, and the results were used solely for research purposes. This declaration ensures that the study adheres to ethical guidelines, protecting both the participants and the integrity of the research.

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